

Table 1: Example for LLM-generated response containing **more than one** incorrect medical knowledge. Clinicians label **Claim 1** as the most erroneous claim, but it is scored higher compared to **Claim 2** and **Claim 3**. Despite these, FAITH actually has successfully identified all these three questionable claims (as indicated by their low scores).

Item	Content
Question	A 60 year old man has 6 months of dry cough and increasing shortness of breath on effort. He was previously fit and well, and is a non -smoker. His temperature is 36.8°C, pulse rate 60 bpm and oxygen saturation 89% breathing air. He has finger clubbing. Cardiac examination is normal, and chest examination reveals bibasal crepitations. Which is the most likely diagnosis?
Options	A. Bronchiectasis B. Extrinsic allergic alveolitis C. Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis D. Lung carcinoma E. Pulmonary tuberculosis
Model Answer	A. Bronchiectasis
Model Explanation	The most likely diagnosis is bronchiectasis. The patient’s symptoms of dry cough and increasing shortness of breath on effort, along with the presence of finger clubbing, suggest a chronic lung disease. Bronchiectasis is characterized by permanent dilation and thickening of bronchi, which can cause chronic cough, sputum production, and recurrent respiratory infections. The bibasal crepitations on chest examination are also consistent with bronchiectasis. Extrinsic allergic alveolitis typically presents with haemoptysis and chest pain , whereas idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis is more likely to present with fine crackles on lung examination. Lung carcinoma can cause symptoms such as coughing up blood or yellow sputum, which are not mentioned in the patient’s presentation. Pulmonary tuberculosis typically presents with fever, night sweats, and weight loss, which are not mentioned in the patient’s presentation.
Clinical Annotation	1. Bronchiectasis typically involves a chronic productive cough, not dry cough. 2. Extrinsic allergic alveolitis typically presents with dyspnoea, dry cough, fatigue, and sometimes flu-like symptoms, rather than haemoptysis and chest pain. 3. Fails to mention finger clubbing, which is a common sign of IPF.
Claim 1	Medical claim: (bronchiectasis, disease_phenotype_positive, dry cough) KG matching: “bronchiectasis” = “bronchiectasis” “dry cough” = “Nonproductive cough” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: bronchiectasis -(indication)->Acetylcysteine -(drug_effect)->Cough -(phenotype_phenotype)->Nonproductive cough FAITH score: 0.0954
Claim 2	Medical claim: (Extrinsic allergic alveolitis, disease_phenotype_positive, haemoptysis) KG matching: “Extrinsic allergic alveolitis” = “extrinsic allergic alveolitis” “haemoptysis” = “Hemoptysis” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: extrinsic allergic alveolitis -(contraindication)->Amiodarone -(drug_effect)->Hemoptysis FAITH score: -0.8962
Claim 3	Medical claim: (Extrinsic allergic alveolitis, disease_phenotype_positive, chest pain) KG matching: “Extrinsic allergic alveolitis” = “extrinsic allergic alveolitis” “chest pain” = “Chest pain” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis -(indication)->Prednisolone -(contraindication)->inherited porphyria -(phenotype_phenotype)->Chest pain FAITH score: -0.5957
Claim n	...
Whole FAITH score	0.2832

Table 2: Example for the response which get a high FAITH score, but is actually incorrect. In this example, all the statements made by the LLM were actually factually correct, and it used these to conclude that the patient has depression. However, the LLM **ignores that the patient’s age is 72**. At this age, all those mentioned symptoms are normal as a result of aging, so it is not correct to conclude that the patient has depression. FAITH is currently unable to detect such errors as it has no access to the original user inputs.

Item	Content
Question	A 72 year old woman has had inability to sleep well for the past 3 years. She gets to sleep by 23:00 but wakes up two or three times in the night and gets up by 07:00. Her husband says that she doesn’t snore. Her BMI is 23 kg/m2. She carries out her normal daytime activities with no daytime somnolence. She is otherwise well. Her MMSE (Mini Mental State Examination) score is 27/30. Which is the most likely cause of her insomnia?
Options	A. Depression B. Early stages of dementia C. Hypomania D. Normal age related sleep pattern E. Obstructive sleep apnoea
Model Answer(Llama 3.1)	A. Depression
Model Explanation (Llama 3.1)	The correct answer is A) Depression. The patient’s symptoms, such as difficulty sleeping well for 3 years, waking up multiple times at night, and being able to carry out normal daytime activities without daytime somnolence, are more consistent with depression than other options. Additionally, the patient’s MMSE score of 27/30 suggests that she is not experiencing significant cognitive impairment, which further supports a diagnosis of depression rather than early stages of dementia (B). The patient’s BMI and lack of snoring also make obstructive sleep apnoea (E) less likely. Hypomania (C) is unlikely given the patient’s symptoms and MMSE score. Normal age-related sleep pattern (D) may be a possibility, but the duration of her insomnia and the fact that she wakes up multiple times at night suggest that there may be an underlying cause beyond just aging.
Clinical Annotation	The patient describes difficulty maintaining sleep (waking multiple times) but has no daytime somnolence and a normal MMSE. This pattern, especially in an older adult, is highly characteristic of a Normal age-related sleep pattern change (D) , not necessarily depression which often involves other symptoms like low mood, anhedonia, or significant daytime fatigue.
Whole FAITH score	0.8857

Table 3: Example of the **entities absent** in KG where the “drug-induced parkinsonism” not existed in PrimeKG. What FAITH does is to flag this and exclude the associated claim from evaluation.

Item	Content
Question	A 60 year old man has 6 months of dry cough and increasing shortness of breath on effort. He was previously fit and well, and is a non-smoker. His temperature is 36.8°C, pulse rate 60 bpm and oxygen saturation 89% breathing air. He has finger clubbing. Cardiac examination is normal, and chest examination reveals bibasal crepitations. Which is the most likely diagnosis?
Options	A. Co-beneldopa B. Entacapone C. Pramipexole D. Procyclidine hydrochloride E. Selegiline hydrochloride
Model Answer	D. Procyclidine hydrochloride
Model Explanation	The patient’s symptoms include a tremor, cogwheel rigidity, and a recent history of worsened symptoms after taking haloperidol, an antipsychotic known to cause drug-induced parkinsonism. The tremor and rigidity suggest extrapyramidal symptoms commonly associated with this condition. Procyclidine hydrochloride , an anticholinergic agent, is commonly used to treat drug-induced parkinsonism by counteracting the dopamine blockade caused by antipsychotics such as haloperidol . Other treatment options like co-beneldopa and pramipexole are used for Parkinson’s disease and not specifically for drug-induced parkinsonism. Entacapone and selegiline are adjunctive treatments in Parkinson’s disease management to enhance or prolong the effect of existing medication but not the first choice for haloperidol-induced EPS. Therefore, the best choice is D) Procyclidine hydrochloride.
Clinical Annotation	The answer is correct, but the reasoning is shallow. It relies mainly on the drug history and misses key clinical details—like bilateral tremor and time frame—that better support drug-induced parkinsonism over Parkinson’s disease.
Claim 1	Medical claim: (haloperidol, disease_phenotype_positive, drug-induced parkinsonism) KG matching: “haloperidol” = “Haloperidol” “drug-induced parkinsonism” : NOT FOUND FAITH score: NaN
Claim 2	Medical claim: (Procyclidine hydrochloride, drug_drug_counteracts, haloperidol) KG matching: “Procyclidine hydrochloride” = “Procyclidine” “haloperidol” = “Haloperidol” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Procyclidine -(drug_drug)->Haloperidol FAITH score: 0.9637
Claim n	...
Whole FAITH score	0.8477